

**CONSERVATION OF PRIORITY
SPECIES OF MARINE
MEGAFUNA
IN GREECE AND ITALY**

D5.6: Webpage

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LIFE22-NAT-EL-LIFE MareNatura
“Conservation of priority species of marine megafauna in Greece and Italy”

**Grant Agreement Project 101113792 –
LIFE22-NAT-EL-LIFE MareNatura – LIFE-2022-SAP-NAT**

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Task Leader:	Michalis Probonas (UoC)
Partners involved:	MEDASSET, HCMR, NCC, ISPRA, NECCA, UoA, ARCHELON, MOm, HOS, NOA, WaterProof
Author(s):	Michalis Probonas (UoC), Popi Baxevani (UoC)
Reviewer(s):	Afroditi Kardamaki (HCMR), Panagiotis Kasapidis (HCMR)
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Abbreviations

ARCHELON	ARCHELON - The Sea Turtle Protection Society of Greece
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HCMR	Hellenic Center for Marine Research
HOS	Hellenic Ornithological Society
ISPRA	Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research
MEDASSET	Mediterranean Association to Save the Sea Turtles
MOM	Hellenic Society for the Study and Protection of the Monk Seal
N2K	Natura 2000
NCC	Nature Conservation Consultants
NECCA	Natural Environment and Climate Change Agency
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
T	Task
UoA	University of the Aegean
UoC	University of Crete
WaterProof	Waterproof Marine Consultancy & Services B.V.
WP	Work Package

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Summary

This document accompanies Deliverable D5.6 - Webpage, which relates to the development of the LIFE MareNatura webpage. The delivery of the project's webpage is part of Task 5.2 - Overall project communication: project webpage, communication materials, etc., sub-task 5.2.2 - Development of the Project's Webpage and pages in social media. The processes involved in the development of the website and the social media pages and the current structure of the LIFE MareNatura webpage are stated in this report. More specifically the steps taken to the development of the webpage are thoroughly discussed and the webpage structure along with a short description of its different components is clearly mentioned.

LIFE MareNatura webpage: www.lifemarenatura.eu.

LIFE MareNatura facebook page:

<https://www.facebook.com/people/LIFE-MareNatura/61557166352873/>

LIFE MareNatura youtube page:

<https://www.youtube.com/@LIFEMareNatura>

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Development process

Development of webpage

The T.5.2.2 - Development of the Project's Webpage and pages in social media sub-task started in accordance with the time schedule of the project and it will continue for the whole project's lifespan (July 2023-June 2029) and during the After-LIFE period (2029-2034).

Preliminary discussions between partners (Communication Team members) about the content and the layout of the website took place online on October 10, 2023 (Picture 1).

Picture 1. Screen shot from the online meeting of the Communication Team on 10/10/2023.

During the meeting the basic structure of the site (see below in Picture 2 the proposed webpage chart) and details about the content were discussed and decided. All partners were informed and asked via E-mail to contribute with photos of the species and pilot areas, as well as with their short CVs in Greek and English and some short texts with specific information about project's species.

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Picture 2: Proposed structure of the LIFE MareNatura website.

For the development of the website a direct treaty procedure was launched in November 2023, with 2 offers to be specifically requested by providers, and the Decision No. 59562/21.12.2023 for the direct treaty to the Contractor “Aegean Solutions Consultants Innovative Applications and New Technologies S.A.” was issued. The Contract with Ref. No. 3234 was signed between the Contract and SARF UoC on January 19, 2024. During the same month, i.e. December 2023, the Internet Domain Name for the hosting of the website (www.lifemarenatura.eu) was purchased by the Contractor for a period of six (6) years, with the provision for a 5-year extension to June 2034, so that it will function in the After-LIFE period. Texts, photos and other material such as the project’s logo, colour pallet, visual graphics etc. (Deliverables of T.5.2.1) were gradually sent to the developer of the site during the period January – February 2024.

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A mini training seminar on the website's management platform was organized and took place between the developer and the UoC communication team at the end of February 2024.

The 1st version of the website was commented by UoC members during the first week of March 2024 and its improvement continued until the beginning of April 2024, with additions and corrections of the content (texts, photos, etc.). The website of the project, www.lifemarenatura.eu (Picture 3), was finally launched on April 12, 2024.

At the moment the website is available in two languages (Greek and English), while the Italian version is expected to be activated by the end of May 2024, as soon as the texts translations will be ready (the direct treaty procedure [with 2 offers] for translations is already in progress).

Picture 3: Screen shot of LIFE MareNatura site homepage.

The website is properly designed to be accessible from portable devices (tablets, notebooks, and smart phones), with emphasis to be given on the best possible appearance and display on smart phones. It is also structured according to specifications of the European Union for use by people with special needs (compliance with WCAG version 2.0 of the W3C), and to be able to cooperate with screen reader tools. A related website certification request has been sent already by the Contractor and relevant answer is still pending.

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Development of Social Media pages

On March 10, 2024, the project’s Facebook Page (Picture 4) and YouTube channel (Picture 5) were created. Their relevant accounts can be seen in the following **Table 1**:

Table 1: Account name and links of project’s Social Media.

Social Media	Name of account	Link
	LIFE MareNatura	https://www.facebook.com/people/LIFE-MareNatura/61557166352873/
	@LIFEMareNatura	https://www.youtube.com/@LIFEMareNatura

Picture 4: Screenshot of LIFE MareNatura Facebook page.

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Picture 5: Screenshot of LIFE MareNatura YouTube channel.

At the same time, project’s e-mail was put into operation. All project’s external communication and promotion will take place through this address: lifemarenatura@gmail.com.

Both project’s social media and the website fulfill all visibility requirements of the EC (EC co-funding, LIFE and Natura logos etc.) and are in accordance with the guidelines of project’s Communication Plan (T.5.1). The electronic tools of LIFE MareNatura will be updated in regular basis with news, announcements of the project’s events and other relative news while in a separate field all deliverables of the project (when public) will be uploaded and available for stakeholders and general public as soon as they are completed.

All partners have been committed to contribute in the updates and promote and share these tools with their collaborators and networks.

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Webpage structure

The delivered webpage is divided into five (5) sections which are visible as a header bar menu. Each section - with the exception of home - is divided into subsections and can be viewed as dropdown menu when the mouse moves over the section name. This allows the user to navigate on the different subsections more easily. The 5 sections of the webpage are: Home, Project, Species/Pilot Areas, Multimedia and News/Events. More specifically, the structure of the sections and subsections of the webpage is as illustrated on Table 1.

Table 2. Illustration of the menu bar with the five sections and their subsections exactly below as shown in LIFE MareNatura webpage (<https://www.lifemarenatura.eu>).

Home	Project	Species/ Pilot Areas	Multimedia	News/Events
	Description	Species	Photo Gallery	News
	Partners	Sites	Videos	Events
	Actions	Descriptions	Media Kit	International Conference
	Objectives - Results		School Kit	Summer school
	Networking		Info material	
	Deliverables			

Description of webpage parts

Following a short description of the content of the sections and subsections of LIFE MareNatura webpage:

Home

The home page has a short description of LIFE MareNatura project, two hyperlinks (visible as box selections) which take the user to the Species page and the Sites' descriptions page and at the bottom the most recent news & events.

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Project

Description

A general description of the LIFE MareNatura project, its scope and goals.

Partners

Short descriptions of the consortium beneficiaries involved in the project.

Actions

Brief descriptions of the 6 Work Packages (WP) and what they entail.

Objectives – Results

Description of the project objectives and expected results.

Networking

Under construction.

Deliverables

A list of deliverables per WP. If the deliverable is marked as public in the GA, it will be uploaded to the website, thus made available to all users.

Species/Pilot Areas

Species

This part includes the 9 priority megafauna species of the project. Each species is accompanied with a brief description on its biology & ecology, distribution, population data and most common threats.

Sites Descriptions

This sub-section includes the 44 N2K project sites of LIFE MareNatura project. A map of the study area with the 44 N2K project sites is displayed. Each project site is displayed with its N2K code, name and a photo within a box. By selecting a project site (clicking on the box), the user is redirected to the relevant information of the selected N2K site on the Biodiversity – Information System for Europe website: <https://biodiversity.europa.eu/>.

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Multimedia

Photo Gallery

Photo gallery of each species.

Videos

It is not available yet – videos in development.

Media Kit

Includes briefs for journalists, project updates and achievements.

School Kit

Currently under development. This sub-section will include the material and specialized apps which will be produce for young children.

Info material

Disseminating material produced by the project such as infographics, for the general public.

News/Events

News

Includes the project news.

Events

Includes the events organized by the LIFE MareNatura project and other event in which the project participate in.

International Conference

Under development. This sub-section relates to the International Conference which will be organized by LIFE MareNatura project.

Marine Conservation School

Under development. This sub-section relates to the Marine Conservation School which will take place in various locations from Year 1 and until Year 5 of LIFE MareNatura project.

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